

Productivity Effect from Investing in Human Capital Part 1 of 2

Louangrath, P.I. ★

About the author

★Louangrath, P.I. is an Assistant Professor in Business Administration at Bangkok University, Bangkok, Thailand. He could be reached by email at: Lecturepedia@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to provide analyses of the effects of investing in human capital at the national and firm levels. The analysis of firm level focuses on labor productivity as the indicator for returns on investing in human capital. The scope of this paper is confined to one research question: “Under what circumstance should a firm invest in human capital?” Using per capita GDP as output and minimum wage as input, the national level analysis serves as a macroeconomic context for firm level study of productivity. For firm level analysis, revenue and cost of good sold were used to determine the level of productivity. Secondary data from the IMF was used for national productivity analysis. Financial reports from Stock Exchange of Thailand for the years 2014, 2015 and 2016 were used for firm level analysis. Thirty listed companies were randomly selected from 100 companies in the SET100 index. The findings show that the national productivity and efficiency levels are higher than those of the firms. Thailand has a national productivity level of 1.85 ± 0.08 and labor efficiency of 0.85 ± 0.08 while the sample firms show a mean productivity of 1.46 ± 0.39 and labor efficiency: 0.46 ± 0.39 . The difference between the national and firm levels may be due to multiplicative effect. The firm’s labor productivity and efficiency is significantly lower than the national level, $p < 0.003$.

Keywords: Efficiency, human capital, productivity

JEL Code: C51, C52, E01

CITATION:

Louangrath, P.I. (2018). “Productivity Effect from Investing in Human Capital - Part 1 of 2.” *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 4, No. 2: pp. 49-63. (Apr. – Jun. 2018); ISSN: 2415-0371.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This research is presented in 2 parts. This paper represents part 1 of 2 parts. In part 1, we identified the productivity at the national and firm levels. In part 2, we will examine the impact of training on wage bill and productivity in detailed. Throughout this paper, we assumed that firms train their employees uniformly without differentiating skill levels.

One of the country's macroeconomic objectives is to increase the national output as measured by the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP). At the national level, the economy demands a productive workforce. At the firm level, companies demand productive workers. Productive workforce or productive workers refers to the level of productivity. Productivity is defined as the ratio of output to input. The productivity level of all workers in a firm represents the firm's productivity. The productivity of all firms represents the productivity in the industry or sector. Likewise, the productivity of all sectors represents the productivity of the economy.

At the national level, we are using Thailand 4.0 as a proxy for our discussion. Thailand 4.0 is an economic development policy aiming to achieve economic prosperity, social well-being, human values and environmental protection. In order to achieve these goal the policy calls for the raising of competitiveness in four main sectors. In the agricultural sector, Thailand 4.0 calls for the transformation of traditional farming to "smart farming." Traditional SMEs will be transformed into "smart SMEs." Where the economy had long been trapped in low value services, Thailand 4.0 wants the country to produce "high value services." Lastly, unskilled labor will be transformed into "skilled labor." In this paper, we are focusing on the labor element of Thailand 4.0 as part of the discussion of investing in human capital.

At the firm level we attempt to answer a basic question: "*whether investing in human capital leads to increase productivity?*" This paper argues that investing in human capital leads to an increase in productivity only among skilled workforce. For unskilled workers, investing in human capital, in a form of training and education, leads to insignificant increase in productivity at best; at worst, it is an economic waste. We qualified this assertion by applying it to private firms. In the case of government-back retraining and retooling of workers to prevent unemployment or worker's dislocation, we make no assessment as it is beyond the scope of this paper. This paper provides proof of these two points by analyzing the impact of training on productivity at firm level; we extend the conclusion to the national economy by inference. Thailand 4.0 economic development policy of Thailand is used as proxy to carry the analysis and discussion for country level analysis. For firm level analysis, 30 companies from Thailand's SET100 index were randomly selected for case studies.

2.0 LITERATURE

This paper discusses investing in human capital in the context of economic development. From this macro-level analysis, we can trace its implementation to the firm level. In order to appreciate the role and importance of investing in human capital, it is imperative to see it in the context of economic development model. By looking at the role of human capital from the perspective of a national economy, one could understand its role better at a firm level. The link between the national economy and firm operation is one which we commonly discuss as internal and external factors analysis. The literature review is comprised of two parts. Part 1 (sec. 2.1) examines the origin of human capital as an economic indicator for development. Part 2 (sec. 2.2) looks at human capital in a form of skills in employees and its implication on firm productivity.

2.1 Neo-classical basis of human capital

The Solow-Swan economic development model is introduced as the backdrop for our discussion in investing in human capital. The element of labor in the Solow-Swan model is the basis from which investing in human capital takes its root. The Solow-Swan model was introduced as a response to the inadequacy of the classical model of economic development (Sato, 1964). The Solow-Swan growth model makes the following assumptions: (i) there is a single output using two inputs namely

labor and capital; and (ii) the elasticity of substitution must be asymptotically equal to one. The model is formally given by:

$$Y(t) = K(t)^\alpha A(t)L(t)^{1-\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where t = time period, α = elasticity of output with respect to capital where the range is $0 < \alpha < 1$; $Y(t)$ = total production at period t ; A = labor augmented technology or “knowledge”; and AL = effective labor (Solow, 1956). The model assumes that all factors are employed with initial condition of $A(0)$, $K(0)$ and $L(0)$. Labor and technology are growth at a rate of:

$$L(t) = L(0)e^{nt} \quad (2)$$

$$A(t) = A(0)e^{gt} \quad (3)$$

The number of effective labor is defined as $A(t)L(t)$ with a growth rate of $(n + g)$. The stock of capital depreciates at a constant rate of δ . Only a fraction of the output is consumed: $cY(t)$ where $0 < c < 1$. What is left from consumption is saved. The saved share of the output is $s = 1 - c$ which is used for investment. Thus, the capital stock at a given period t is given as:

$$\hat{K}(t) = sY(t) - \delta K(t) \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{K} = \frac{dK(t)}{dt}$ or the change in capital stock with respect to time. Since the production function $Y(K, A, L)$ has a constant return to scale (Gelles and Douglas, 1996), it can be written as output per effective unit of labor, thus:

$$y(t) = \frac{Y(t)}{A(t)L(t)} = k(t)^\alpha \quad (5)$$

where k = capital intensity or capital stock per unit of labor. The long-run pattern is given by the Solow-Swan model:

$$\hat{K}(t) = sK(t)^\alpha - (n + g + \delta)K(t) \quad (6)$$

where $sK(t)^\alpha = sY(t)$ which is the actual investment per unit of effective labor. The fraction s of the output per unit of effective labor $y(t)$ that is saved and invested; $(n + g + \delta)$ = break-even investment or the amount of investment that must be invested to prevent K from falling.

Equation 6 implies that $K(t)$ converges to steady-state value of K^* defined by: $sK(t)^\alpha = (n + g + \delta)K(t)$. At the steady-state, there is no increase or decrease of capital intensity:

$$K^* = \left(\frac{s}{n + g + \delta} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}} \quad (7)$$

The Solow-Swan model predicts that an economy will converge to a balanced-growth equilibrium. The growth of the output per worker is determined solely by the rate of technological

progress. Since $\frac{K(t)}{Y(t)} = k(t)^{1-a}$ at equilibrium K^* , the rate of change of capital with respect to output is $\frac{K(t)}{Y(t)} = \frac{s}{n+g+\delta}$. At equilibrium, capital/output rate depends on *savings, growth, and depreciation rates*. Solow-Swan allows us to track the effect of the economic growth from changes in technology, capital and labor (Haines and Nawaz, 2006). Under Solow-Swan model, the marginal product of capital in rich and poor countries is the same (Caselli and Feyrer, 2007). Therefore, poor countries are poor because of low productivity. This low productivity may be explained by the low level of human capital (Lucas, 1990).

The Solow-Swan model has been modified by Mankiw-Romer-Weil by adding human capital to the equation (Mankiw *et al.*, 1992):

$$Y(t) = K(t)^\alpha H(t)^\beta A(t)L(t)^{1-\alpha-\beta} \tag{8}$$

where $H(t)$ is the stock of human capital which, like physical capital, depreciates over time at a rate of δ . The savings in investment in physical and human capital is: $S = s_K + s_H$. The dynamic equations are given by:

$$\bar{k} = s_K k^\alpha h^\beta - (n+g+\delta)k \tag{9}$$

$$\bar{h} = s_H k^\alpha h^\beta - (n+g+\delta)h \tag{10}$$

The steady-state growth path is $\bar{k} = \bar{h} = 0$ which means that $s_K k^\alpha h^\beta - (n+g+\delta)k = 0$ and $s_H k^\alpha h^\beta - (n+g+\delta)h = 0$ at steady-state. Therefore, the steady-state k and h is:

$$k^* = \left(\frac{s_K^{1-\beta} S_H^\beta}{n+g+\delta} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha-\beta}} \tag{11}$$

$$s^* = \left(\frac{s_K^\alpha S_H^{1-\alpha}}{n+g+\delta} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha-\beta}} \tag{12}$$

$$y^* = (k^*)^\alpha (h^*)^\beta \tag{13}$$

It has been shown that the effect of human capital is greater at the national level as indicated by economic growth than it is on a micro-level as measured by worker's salary (Klenow and Andres, 1997). It is true that when firm trains its employees, the effect of such training does not always translate into an increase in revenue. This is particularly true when the employee leaves the current firm to join another. This lateral transfer results the absorption of skilled worker by one firm at the expense of another, who invested in the training of that worker. However, at the national level, the increase in skills of the workforce contributes to the aggregate output. This aggregate effect is consistent with Solow-Swan model. Thus, human capital and technology had multiplicative effect on production (Breton, 2013). Therefore, even if the effect of human capital (β) does not

directly cause the training firm's output to increase, its indirect effect to increase the national output in the country is worth investing in human capital.

2.2 Applying national development to firm investment in human capital

Through the Solow-Swan model of economic development, we established the rationale under which investing in human capital at the firm level is discussed. From a top-down view, the logic of the argument is that human capital is a key to economic growth and development. At the firm level, this human capital may be accumulated through investing in employees. We focus on a practical issue in investing in human capital by examining the effect of employee training. We define training cost as input and the revenue of the firm as output. If the firm is bound by profit maximization objective, the training of employees should lead to increase in revenue. We assert that although there might be an increase in revenue, this increase is not optimized as long as there is a mixture of skilled and unskilled workers in the firm. Optimization may be possible if all workers in the firm are skilled. However, this is not the case in all firms.

From equation (8): $Y(t) = K(t)^\alpha H(t)^\beta A(t)L(t)^{1-\alpha-\beta}$, we are interested in the human capital term, $H(t)^\beta$ and its effect on the firm's output. The human capital term $H(t)^\beta$ at a national level will be equated to the aggregate labor term, $\hat{L}_{it}^{\beta L}$, in the firm context in equation (14, *infra*): $Y_{it} = A_{it} \hat{L}_{it}^{\beta L} K_{it}^{\beta k}$. At the national level, human capital may be written as:

$$H(t)^\beta = \frac{Y(t)}{K(t)^\alpha A(t)L(t)^{1-\alpha-\beta}}$$

From (14, *infra*), the labor aggregate term may be written as:

$$\hat{L}_{it}^{\beta L} = \frac{Y_{it}}{A_{it} K_{it}^{\beta k}}$$

The ratio of $\hat{L}_{it}^{\beta L} : H(t)^\beta$ will become our link from the firm level to the national level, and vice versa. As we examine $\hat{L}_{it}^{\beta L}$, we will look at the impact of training on labor productivity at a firm level.

3.0 DATA

The data used in this research comes from various secondary sources. From the IMF's annual report on World Economic Outlook 2017, we extracted macro-economic data for the ASEAN country (IMF, 2017). While Thailand is used as a proxy country, we used ASEAN's 10 economies as a cohort in order to examine Thailand's economic data with a group benchmark. Additional data was extracted from the ADB's annual report on sustainable development (ADB, 2017). This macroeconomic data came from a period of 10 years spanning from 2008 to 2017.

At the national level, we used the annual GDP as indicator for the national output. The minimum wage was used as input cost. At the firm level, we used the firm's income statement as the basic document to provide us with the proxy data. There are 100 firms listed in the Stock Exchange of Thailand (SET), we randomly select 30 companies to use as proxy for the firm level analysis. The firm data used consists of sales and cost of good sold. Sales represent the firm's output. COGS represent the firm's input where direct labor is part of COGS. Since the data is a secondary data taken from the company Fact Sheet at www.settrade.com, we have no way of extracting direct labor cost from COGS; thus the entire amount of COGS is used.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach of this paper follows two key prior publications by Bello *et al.* (2011) and Konings and Stijn (2010). Bello *et al.* decomposes the per capita GDP in order to obtain labor productivity per worker. We extend this per worker analysis through Konings and Stijn's work on the impact of working training on the firm and worker's salary.

4.1 Decomposing per capita GDP on obtain per hour basis

In Bello *et al.*, per capita GDP per worker may be obtained by:

$$\frac{Y}{P} = \frac{Y}{nE} \left(\frac{E}{p} \right)^n \quad (14)$$

where Y/P = per capita GDP per labor hour (labor productivity), E/P = employment of population ratio, and n = number of hours per week.

The labor productivity (GDP per hour) may be decomposed into its components in the Cobb-Douglas production function by:

$$Y = AK^a (hEn)^{1-a} \quad (15)$$

where A = factor of productivity, K = physical capital, and h = human capital per worker. Thus, the GDP per hour may be obtained by using the Klenow-Rodriguez-Claire (1997) approach:

$$\frac{Y}{nE} = A^{1-a} \left(\frac{K}{Y} \right)^{1-a} h^a \quad (16)$$

In Bello *et al.*, the study involved the comparison of Venezuela and the US, in this paper we are looking at Thailand and the ASEAN and Thailand and the OECD, we follow Bello *et al.*'s approach in this comparison between economies i and j , thus:

$$\frac{y_i}{y_j} = \left(\frac{A_i}{A_j} \right)^{1-a} \left(\frac{(K/Y)_i}{(K/Y)_j} \right)^{1-a} \left(\frac{h_i}{h_j} \right)^a \quad (17)$$

Bello *et al.*'s approach takes the GDP and break it down to per hour basis; since this is economy-to-worker, we used it as the threshold value for which the observed value is compared since their work. The work of Konings and Stijn will guide us through the issue of worker's training impacting the firm's productivity.

The methodological structure outlined in sections 4.2 and 4.3 is based on the work of Konings and Stijn. The work of Konings and Stijn consists of three components, namely (i) impact of training on productivity, (ii) impact of training on worker's salary, and (iii) estimation method for impact measurement. Although, we use Konings and Stijn as the basis for firm level measurement, we take the issue back to its basic query: should firm invest in human capital? If so, under what circumstances should that investment is made?

4.2 Impact of training on productivity

Given a firm i during an operational period t , the firm's output is a function of labor L and capital K . The output function in the Cobb-Douglas production function form (Cobb and Douglas, 1928; and Douglas, 1976) is given by:

$$Y_{it} = A_{it} \hat{L}_{it}^{\beta_L} K_{it}^{\beta_K} \quad (18)$$

where \hat{L}_{it} = quality of aggregate labor, K_{it} = capital of firm, and A_{it} = Hicks neutral technical efficiency (Hicks, 1966, and Wood & Woods, 1989). The logarithm of the output function may be written as:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_L \hat{\ell}_{it} + \beta_K k_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (19)$$

The fixed component a_{it} may be decomposed to obtain the productivity level, and μ_{it} represents the firm's output deviating from the mean.

The argument in (18) and (19) assumes that the labor force in the firm is homogenous. However, in practice, this assumption would have to be relaxed so that the labor term is comprised of trained and untrained employees: $\hat{L} = \text{trained} + \text{untrained}$; thus, the relative or marginal productivity of trained and untrained employees is defined as:

$$\phi_T = \frac{\partial Y / \partial L_T - \partial Y / \partial L_U}{\partial Y / \partial L_U} \quad (20)$$

which could be rewritten as:

$$\phi_T = \frac{MP_T - MP_U}{MP_U} \quad (21)$$

where L_U = untrained employees, and L_T = trained employees. We can now formally write the labor aggregate as:

$$\hat{L} = L_U + (1 + \phi_T)L_T \quad \text{or} \quad \hat{L} = L \left(1 + \phi_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) \right) \quad (22)$$

where L = total employees in a firm where the fraction of the trained employees to the total employees in the firm is L_T / L . By substitution, we now have:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_L \ell + \beta_L \ln \left(1 + \phi_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) \right) + \beta_K k + \mu \quad (23)$$

When $\phi_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right)$ is small, the firm's output may be approximated as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_L \ell + \beta_L \phi_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) + \beta_K k + \mu \quad (24)$$

The positive sign of the coefficient on the share of trained employees indicates the marginal product of trained employees is higher than that of the untrained.

Thus far, the argument assumes that training is discrete, i.e. either the employees had training or not. However, in practice, the level of training is not discrete. There is variation of training level among employees; therefore, the equation must accommodate this variation in a continuous and non-discrete fashion. Mincer (1974) asserts that the individual employee j working in firm i earns a wage that is a function of the level of his/her training, thus:

$$\ln(W_j) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_T T_j + v_j \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the average wage bill of the firm may be given by: $\sum_j \exp(\alpha_0 + \alpha_T T_j + v_j)$ where T_j is the training hours of employee j .

If the firm's objective is to maximize profit, the labor term on the production function should have the same form as the wage bill (Frazer, 2001):

$$\hat{L} = \sum_j \exp(\beta_1 + \beta_T T_j) \quad (26)$$

The production function then becomes:

$$Y = A \left(\sum_j \exp(\beta_1 + \beta_T T_j) \right)^{\beta_\ell} K^{\beta_k} \quad (27)$$

where β_k is the contribution of the individual employee j to the aggregate labor. This contribution varies with the level of training: $\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial T_j} = \beta_T$. By taking the logarithm, we obtained:

$$y = \beta_\ell \beta_1 + \beta_\ell \ln \left(\sum_j \exp(\beta_T T_j) \right) + \beta_k k + a \quad (28)$$

The first order of Taylor approximation of the labor term results in a log-linear equation that can be estimated. The logarithm of output is a function of the logarithm of the amount of labor and capital, and the average training hours of all employees in a firm:

$$y = \beta_0^* + \beta_\ell \ell + \beta_\ell \beta_T \bar{T} + \beta_k k + \mu \quad (29)$$

where β_T measures the labor aggregate changes with training intensity, and β_ℓ is the labor in production where the impact of output is $\frac{\partial y}{\partial T} = \beta_\ell \beta_T$. This last term represents the percentage output changes in responses to the variation in average training intensity of the workforce.

4.3 Impact of training on wages

Hellerstein (1999) provides a firm level wage bill. The measurement for wage differentials between trained and untrained employees can be made. Recall that Mincer's wage equation was:

$$W_j = W_U D_{j,U} + W_T D_{j,T} \quad (30)$$

where W_j = wage per employee j ; W_U = wage of untrained employee; W_T = wage of trained employee, and $D_{j,U}$ = dummy variable set equal to 1 if the employee is untrained. Thus, the wage bill for the entire firm is given as:

$$\bar{W}L = W_U L_U + W_T L_T \quad (31)$$

That is to say that the wage bill for the firm is a function of wage per untrained employee multiplied by the total number of untrained employees plus the wage of trained employees multiplied by the total number of trained employees. Equation (27) may be rewritten as:

$$\bar{W}L = W_U L \left(1 + \lambda_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) \right) \quad (32)$$

The term λ_T represents the relative wage premium for trained employee compared to the untrained; it is calculated by: $\lambda_T = \frac{W_T - W_U}{W_U}$. Now, if we divide both sides of the equation by the number of employees (L), we obtain:

$$\bar{w} = w_U + \ln \left(1 + \lambda_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) \right) \quad (33)$$

If $\ln(1+x)$ could be approximated by x if x is small, then (33) becomes:

$$\bar{w} = w_U + \lambda_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) \quad (34)$$

Now, let x be a vector of controlled variable in case there is a variation due to imperfection of the labor market, then the firm's wage bill becomes:

$$w = w_U + \lambda_T \left(\frac{L_T}{L} \right) + x\gamma + \varepsilon \quad (35)$$

There is a positive association between average wage at the firm level and the share of trained employees. This is the implication of a positive wage premium for trained employees.

If there is a variation in training intensity, the firm's wage level equation then becomes:

$$\bar{w} = w_U + \alpha_T \bar{T} \quad (36)$$

where \bar{T} is the training cost per employee, α_T is the wage premium changes with intensity of training: $\frac{\partial w}{\partial T}$, and w_U is the average wage of employees with no training. Recall from (35) that we

used $x\gamma$ as an indication of error term produced by the labor market imperfection; thus, the firm's average wage bill in (36) with $x\gamma$ may be written as:

$$\bar{w} = w_U + \alpha_T \bar{T} + x\gamma + e \tag{37}$$

In the original work of Konings and Stijn, an estimation method was explained. However, in this paper, we use only the foundational work on impact analysis in Konings and Stijn, for estimation, we employ NK landscape simulation to approximate the values by using the following test statistic:

$$Z_{obs} = \frac{F(X) - 0.50}{\sqrt{\frac{N}{12}}} \tag{38}$$

Compared to the theoretical value of:

$$Z^* = \frac{(\mu - \sigma)\phi(x) - 0.50}{\sqrt{\frac{N}{12}}} \tag{39}$$

The following decision rule is used: $H_0 : Z_{obs} < Z^*$ means no significant increase in productivity and $H_A : Z_{obs} \geq Z^*$ means significant increase in productivity.

4.4 Application of the employee productivity to investing in human capital

We do not question the overall effect of training on workers' productivity; however, we argue that workers' training should be more targeted in order to optimize productivity. To support this argument, we present two scenarios of skilled and unskilled workers in the same hypothetical firm. In order to optimize productivity, the training, and hence human capital investment, must be specifically targeted through the SMART approach: (i) specific, (ii) measurable, (iii) attainable, (iv) relevance, and (iv) time. To provide wholesale training to employees without considering their skill levels would lead to economic waste.

Human capital investment could not be separated from human resource management. The objectives of HR department are to acquire, train, and retain employees for the firm as part of its operational support function. The hiring of inexperienced and unskilled employees leads to higher cost in training and lower level of productivity. Trainings provided to unskilled workers generally produce lower returns for the firm. In contrast, if the firm hires more experienced and skilled workers, albeit at a higher wage bill, without additional training, productivity level is generally higher. With additional training, i.e. human capital investment, dollar-for-dollar, the firm could optimize its returns from skilled workers. The higher wage bill in hiring skilled workers may be offset by the increased productivity.

5.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data from 10 years of Thailand's per capita GDP and minimum wage (Table 1) and that of 10 proxy companies from SET100 represents the current situation or prior to Thailand 4.0 policy. One of the requisite of Thailand 4.0 in transforming Thailand into a First World economy is investing in human capital. We saw that at a national level, human capital was considered a significant factor for national development in Solow-Swan model then later reinforced by Mankiw-Romer-Weil. In order to succeed at the national level, Thailand 4.0 must also mobilize firm to invest in human capital as

part of policy-to-practice campaign. In so doing, we ask a preemptive question: “Under what circumstances does investing in human capital lead to increase productivity within a firm?”

Table 1. Per capita GDP of Thailand

Year	Per Capita GDP (Output)	Minimum Wage (Input)	Productivity $P = Output \div Input$	Efficiency $E = (O - I) / I$
2008	4,379.53*	2,215.22**	1.98	0.98
2009	4,207.58	2,129.37	1.98	0.98
2010	5,065.38	2,337.96	2.17	1.17
2011	5,482.40	2,539.37	2.16	1.16
2012	5,850.30	3,476.02	1.68	0.68
2013	6,157.36	3,516.77	1.75	0.75
2014	5,921.09	3,325.12	1.78	0.78
2015	5,799.39	3,153.28	1.84	0.84
2016	5,899.42	3,060.36	1.93	0.93
2017	6,265.29	3,138.045	2.00	1.00
<i>Mean</i>	<i>5,502.77</i>	<i>2,889.15</i>	<i>1.93</i>	<i>0.93</i>
<i>S</i>	<i>721.26</i>	<i>531.98</i>	<i>0.16</i>	<i>0.16</i>

*World Economic Outlook 2017 (IMF, 2017). **Thailand minimum wage: 300 Baht per person per day. Exchange rate at 35 Baht per USD.

At the national level, our situation analysis shows that the average productivity is 1.93 ± 0.16 . This number is obtained by using the minimum wage as input and the per capita GDP as output. If minimum wage is used as a base, every unit of input produces 1.93 units of output. Thailand had achieved an increasing return to scale by a factor of 1.93. Productivity under this approach does not provide adequate information on the effectiveness of labor in Thailand. We divided the difference between output and input by input to obtain a more meaningful measure for productivity: 0.93 ± 0.16 . In the past 10 years, none was observed that there had been significant efficiency.

The national productivity level, obtained from the annual GDP from 2008 to 2017 as tabulated in table 1, was put into NK landscape optimization equation to determine the local optima. The result of this second level verification is presented in Table 2. Among the series of local optima, as presented by $F(Z)$ opt, there is no significant *locale*. The threshold for the decision rule is $pValue < 0.05$; as shown in Table 2, all points are larger than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant local optimum. We conclude that in the period between 2008 and 2017, the productivity of Thailand’s GDP was not optimized. This implication of this finding is that the economy may have been underperformed or that the economy was not exploited to its full potential.

Table 2. NK Landscape optimization of productivity level 2008-2017

Year	Productivity	F(Z)	Z(obs) opt	F(Z) opt	pValue opt
2008	1.98	0.6257	0.14	0.5547	0.45*
2009	1.98	0.6257	0.14	0.5547	0.45
2010	2.17	0.9299	0.47	0.6811	0.32
2011	2.16	0.9213	0.46	0.6777	0.32
2012	1.68	0.0668	(0.47)	0.3176	0.68
2013	1.75	0.1418	(0.39)	0.3475	0.65
2014	1.78	0.1868	(0.34)	0.3658	0.63
2015	1.84	0.2993	(0.22)	0.4131	0.59
2016	1.93	0.5072	0.01	0.5032	0.50
2017	2.00	0.6706	0.19	0.5741	0.43
<i>MEAN</i>	<i>1.93</i>	<i>0.50</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.50</i>	<i>0.50</i>

<i>SD</i>	<i>1.92</i>	<i>0.48</i>	<i>(0.02)</i>	<i>0.49</i>	<i>0.51</i>
-----------	-------------	-------------	---------------	-------------	-------------

*Using 95% confidence interval, the threshold for *pValue* is $p = 0.05$.

Armed with the national figure, we examine 30 companies randomly selected from the stock market in Thailand and found that the ratio of output to input is 1.46 ± 0.39 and the percent change of output to input is 0.46 ± 0.39 (Table 3). By productivity ratio and efficiency, firms performed below national average. Among the 30 companies, two companies show significantly high efficiency (AOT and SAWAD). This finding presents a challenge for Thailand 4.0 policy aiming to transform the economy into the First World Economy. This challenge may be summarized in two statements: (i) The national economy falls below FWE standard, and (ii) domestic firm falls below the national average.

Table 3. Labor and productivity and efficiency of 30 listed companies in Thailand

Company Tickers	Revenue* Output	Expenses** Input	Productivity r / C	Efficiency $(r - C) / C$
ADVANC	152,251.79	107,272.20	1.42	0.42
AOT	44,172.13	20,519.76	2.15	1.15
BCH	5,859.57	4,636.35	1.26	0.26
BEAUTY	1,890.64	1,016.90	1.86	0.86
BEM	12,025.21	6,893.04	1.74	0.74
CBG	8,388.95	6,359.97	1.32	0.32
CHG	3,154.46	2,459.83	1.28	0.28
CK	37,877.10	35,756.49	1.06	0.06
CPF	437,286.39	393,978.88	1.11	0.11
DTAC	86,881.66	69,995.12	1.24	0.24
GLOW	62,349.67	53,055.45	1.18	0.18
GUNKUL	3,514.95	2,932.01	1.20	0.20
KBANK	114,601.70	56,998.36	2.01	1.01
KCE	12,510.19	9,717.11	1.29	0.29
KTB	126,793.29	74,704.05	1.70	0.70
KTC	6,647.39	3,253.28	2.04	1.04
LH	28,161.58	21,366.68	1.32	0.32
LPN	14,698.60	11,790.90	1.25	0.25
MINT	43,524.27	26,504.80	1.64	0.64
RS	3,720.03	2,994.79	1.24	0.24
S	1,915.01	1,425.00	1.34	0.34
SAWAD	2,925.67	1,133.81	2.58	1.58
SCN	2,238.55	1,905.21	1.17	0.17
STEC	19,311.79	18,038.28	1.07	0.07
SUPER	1,350.02	693.65	1.95	0.95
TASCO	35,633.95	33,402.59	1.07	0.07
TISCO	17,263.32	10,443.25	1.65	0.65
TPIPL	28,393.75	25,258.50	1.12	0.12
TRUE	117,571.97	99,633.49	1.18	0.18
VIBHA	5,345.88	4,197.36	1.27	0.27
<i>Mean</i>	<i>47,941.98</i>	<i>36,944.57</i>	<i>1.46</i>	<i>0.46</i>
<i>S</i>	<i>84,992.86</i>	<i>73,742.37</i>	<i>0.39</i>	<i>0.39</i>

*Revenue defines output. **Cost of good sold (COGS) is used as input. Labor cost is included in COGS. The data is the 3 years average: 2014, 2015 and 2016. www.settrade.com. Unit in million Baht. Exchange rate: 35 Baht per USD.

Similar to our treatment of the national data, we subjected the productivity level of the 30 firms to NK landscape optimization determination. The results are presented in Table 4. The average local optima is 0.49 ± 0.07 with the mean pValue of $0.51 \leq 0.07$ where the threshold value for the pValue under 95% confidence interval is 0.05. We concluded that there was no firm operating with optimum productivity level.

Table 4. NK Landscape optimization of productivity level of 30 firms

Firm	Productivity	F(Z)	Z(obs) opt	F(Z) opt	pValue opt
ADVANC	1.42	0.46	(0.02)	0.49	0.51
AOT	2.15	0.96	0.29	0.62	0.38
BCH	1.26	0.30	(0.12)	0.45	0.55
BEAUTY	1.86	0.85	0.22	0.59	0.41
BEM	1.74	0.77	0.17	0.57	0.43
CBG	1.32	0.36	(0.09)	0.47	0.53
CHG	1.28	0.32	(0.11)	0.46	0.54
CK	1.06	0.15	(0.22)	0.41	0.59
CPF	1.11	0.18	(0.20)	0.42	0.58
DTAC	1.24	0.29	(0.13)	0.45	0.55
GLOW	1.18	0.24	(0.17)	0.43	0.57
GUNKUL	1.20	0.25	(0.16)	0.44	0.56
KBANK	2.01	0.92	0.27	0.61	0.39
KCE	1.29	0.33	(0.11)	0.46	0.54
KTB	1.70	0.74	0.15	0.56	0.44
KTC	2.04	0.94	0.28	0.61	0.39
LH	1.32	0.36	(0.09)	0.47	0.53
LPN	1.25	0.30	(0.13)	0.45	0.55
MINT	1.64	0.68	0.12	0.55	0.45
RS	1.24	0.29	(0.13)	0.45	0.55
S	1.34	0.38	(0.08)	0.47	0.53
SAWAD	2.58	1.00	0.32	0.62	0.38
SCN	1.17	0.23	(0.17)	0.43	0.57
STEC	1.07	0.16	(0.22)	0.41	0.59
SUPER	1.95	0.90	0.25	0.60	0.40
TASCO	1.07	0.16	(0.22)	0.41	0.59
TISCO	1.65	0.69	0.12	0.55	0.45
TPIPL	1.12	0.19	(0.20)	0.42	0.58
TRUE	1.18	0.24	(0.17)	0.43	0.57
VIBHA	1.27	0.31	(0.12)	0.45	0.55
<i>MEAN</i>	<i>1.46</i>	<i>0.47</i>	<i>(0.02)</i>	<i>0.49</i>	<i>0.51</i>
<i>SD</i>	<i>0.39</i>	<i>0.29</i>	<i>0.18</i>	<i>0.07</i>	<i>0.07</i>

For the fiscal years 2014, 2014 and 2016, at the national level the productivity level was 1.93 ± 0.16 and efficiency 0.93 ± 0.16 . The sample firm's corresponding figures were 1.46 ± 0.39 for productivity and 0.46 ± 0.39 for efficiency. If we use the national figure as the threshold, the standard score for the thirty sampled firms is $Z = (1.46 - 1.93) / 0.16 = -2.94$ for productivity and $Z = (0.46 - 0.93) / 0.16 = -2.94$; in both cases, the firms perform below national average in productivity and efficiency with the significance level is $p < 0.003$.

6.0 CONCLUSION

In this part 1 of 2 parts research project, we presented our preliminary findings that could give a broad picture of the national and firm levels analysis of productivity. In part 2, we will use our findings I part 1 to analyze the impact of training on wage bill and productivity in detailed. In part 1, we found that the national productivity is higher than that of the firm. This difference may be explained by the multiplicative effect where the firm who invested in training may not directly reap the benefits from the training of the employees if they transfer to other firms or industries. However, wherever these trained employees go they will go with higher skills and would produce higher level of productivity; thus, the over all effects on the economy is the increase in national productivity level. Despite the fact the national productivity level is higher than that of the firm, in this part 1 of the research, through local optimization calculation under NK landscape method we found that both firms and the national economy of Thailand are not operating to its fullest potential. In the context of Thailand 4.0 specifically for Thailand, and for industry 4.0 in general if the method employed in this research is to be duplicated in other economies, the local optima shows that there is a room for further improvement and growth in productivity.

REFERENCES

- Bello, Omar D., Blyde, Juan S. and Restuccia, Diego (2011). “Venezuela's Growth Experience.” *Lat. Am. J. Econ.* **48**(2) (Santiago Nov. 2011); pp. 199-226.
http://www.scielo.cl/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0719-04332011000200005
- Breton, T. R. (2013). “Were Mankiw, Romer, and Weil Right? A Reconciliation of the Micro and Macro Effects of Schooling on Income.” *Macroeconomic Dynamics*. **17**(5): 1023–1054. doi:10.1017/S1365100511000824.
- Caselli, F.; Feyrer, J. (2007). “The Marginal Product of Capital.” *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. **122** (2): 535–68. doi:10.1162/qjec.122.2.535.
- Cobb, C. W.; Douglas, P. H. (1928). “A Theory of Production.” *American Economic Review*. **18** (Supplement): 139–165.
- Douglas, Paul H. (October 1976). “The Cobb-Douglas Production Function Once Again: Its History, Its Testing, and Some New Empirical Values.” *Journal of Political Economy*. **84**(5): 903–916. doi:10.1086/260489.
<http://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/260489>
- Frazer G. (2001) “Linking Firms and Workers: Heterogeneous Labor and Returns to Education.” *Mimeo Yale University*, pp. 1-30.
<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.198.8233&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Gelles, Gregory M.; Mitchell, Douglas W. (1996). “Returns to scale and economies of scale: Further observations.” *Journal of Economic Education*. **27** (3): 259–261. JSTOR 1183297.
- Haines, Joel D.; Sharif, Nawaz M. (2006). “A framework for managing the sophistication of the components of technology for global competition.” *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*. Emerald. **16** (2): 106–121. doi:10.1108/cr.2006.16.2.106.
- Hellerstein, J. K. and D. Neumark (1999). “Sex, wages, and productivity: An empirical analysis of Israeli ...rm-level data.” *International Economic Review* **40**(1): 95.
- Hellerstein, J. K., D. Neumark, and K. R. Troske. (1999). “Wages, Productivity, and Worker Characteristics: Evidence from Plant Level Production Functions and Wage Equations.” *Journal of Labor Economics*, **17**(3): 409-446.
- Hicks, John Richard (1966) [1932]. *The Theory of Wages*. St. Martins Press. ISBN 0-333-02764-7.
- Klenow, P. and A. Rodríguez-Clare (1997), “The Neoclassical Revival in Growth Economics: Has it Gone Too Far?” in B. Bernanke and J. Rotemberg, eds., *NBER Macroeconomics Annual 1997*. MIT Press: Cambridge, MA, pp. 73-102.
- Klenow, Peter J.; Rodriguez-Clare, Andres (January 1997). “The Neoclassical Revival in Growth Economics: Has It Gone Too Far?” In Bernanke, Ben S.; Rotemberg, Julio. NBER

- Macroeconomics Annual 1997, Volume 12. National Bureau of Economic Research. pp. 73–114. ISBN 0-262-02435-7.
- Konings, Jozef and Vanormelingen, Stijn (2010). “The Impact of Training on Productivity and Wages: Firm Level Evidence.” IZA DP No. 4731; Forschungsinstitut zur Zukunft der Arbeit (Institute for the Study of Labor) Discussion Paper No. 4731; January 2010.
- Lucas, Robert (1990). “Why doesn't Capital Flow from Rich to Poor Countries?” *American Economic Review*. **80**(2): 92–96.
- Mankiw, N. Gregory; Romer, David; Weil, David N. (May 1992). “A Contribution to the Empirics of Economic Growth.” *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. **107**(2): 407–437. doi:10.2307/2118477. JSTOR 2118477.
- Mincer, J., (1974). *Schooling, Experience, and Earnings*; pp. 41-63. Columbia Univ. Press, New York.
<http://econpapers.repec.org/bookchap/nbrnberbk/minc74-1.htm>
- Sato, Ryuzo (1964). “The Harrod-Domar Model vs the Neo-Classical Growth Model.” *The Economic Journal*. **74**(294): 380–387. doi:10.2307/2228485. JSTOR 2228485; and Solow, Robert M. (1994). “Perspectives on Growth Theory.” *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. **8**(1): 45–54. doi:10.1257/jep.8.1.45. JSTOR 2138150.
- Solow, Robert M. (February 1956). “A contribution to the theory of economic growth.” *Quarterly Journal of Economics*. Oxford Journals. **70**(1): 65–94. doi:10.2307/1884513. JSTOR 1884513; and Swan, Trevor W. (November 1956). “Economic growth and capital accumulation.” *Economic Record*. Wiley. **32**(2): 334–361. doi:10.1111/j.1475-4932.1956.tb00434.x.
- Wood, John Cunningham; Woods, Ronald N. (1989). *Sir John R. Hicks: Critical Assessments*. Routledge. p. 231. ISBN 0-415-01272-4.

